

INTERFACIAL EVALUATION OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED NANO-COMPOSITES USING ELECTRICAL RESISTANCE MEASUREMENT WITH WETTING TESTS

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ABSTRACT

The use of carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) is rapidly increasing in aerospace and automobile applications. This is in large part due to the increase strength and modulus of carbon fiber composites compared to other materials such as glass fiber composites. The fiber-matrix interface has been found to be important for high strength in composites. Methods that have been studied and developed to improve interfacial property of composites include: the addition of coupling agents, surface modifications, chemical reaction control and use of nano-fillers for reinforcement. During mechanical loading the shape of carbon fibers, in a composite, is altered with a concomitant change in electrical resistance. Carbon fibers are used as sensing elements in CFRP due to their electrical conductivity. In some more advanced studies, in CRFP, the carbon fibers were used for both strain sensing and damage sensing. The basic theory, in such studies, was that the movement of carbon fiber could be detected by electrical resistance measurement. During loading, the extent of contact between carbon fibers in a CF tow is altered, and the electrical resistance changes from its initial value. In this work, interfacial properties of carbon fiber/polymer composites were evaluated by such electrical resistance measurements. During the wetting process of CF tows by the polymer resins, the change in electrical resistance was recorded and analyzed. The test results for different carbon fibers and polymer resins exhibited different trends. The electrical resistance change was associated with the different wetting conditions, and the interfacial properties were predicted by these electrical resistance measurements. CF tow/epoxy exhibited the poorest carbon tow wettability, the smallest change in resistance and the poorest IFSS and ILSS. For the four systems studied, the relative change in each of these quantities for the materials of a given composite was roughly proportional to the other measured quantities. This may have some very significant practical importance. It may point the way to use quick easy tests to screen and predict other behaviors for composites of different materials and/or processes. Perhaps a simple resistance change test might be used to predict and select good candidate materials, surface processing techniques for high strength composite applications. The proportional relationship between interfacial adhesion and electrical resistance change was obtained by trend fitting line analyses. Ultimately, it was demonstrated that mechanical properties related to interfacial properties might potentially be predicted by electrical resistance measurement and studies of wetting behavior, using empirical formulas and correlations.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) is rapidly increasing in aerospace and automobile

applications. This is in large part due to the increase strength and modulus of carbon fiber composites compared to other materials such as glass fiber composites [1-3]. The fiber-matrix interface has been found to be important for high strength in composites. Methods that have been studied and developed to improve interfacial property of composites include: addition of coupling agents, surface modifications, chemical reaction control and use of nano fillers for reinforcement [4-7].

A large number of mechanical test methods have been used to evaluate the interfacial properties of composites, including macroscopic methods [interlaminar shear stress (ILSS) measurements] and microscopic methods [interfacial shear stress (IFSS) measurements] [8-10]. These two evaluation methods have the advantage of yielding easily interpreted interfacial bonding force results but on the other hand they do consume a great amount of time in sample manufacture, preparation and testing.

Thermodynamics approaches, such as contact angle measurements, which are very different from the mechanical evaluation methods just discussed, have also been used to study interfacial properties. In these tests the static contact angle between different liquid types (polarity, non-polarity solvents) and a solid surface was measured for use in calculating surface energies, work of adhesion and spreading coefficient. Contact angle measurements have the advantage of providing a non-destructive method of interfacial evaluation of the interface between a matrix and reinforcement. It has been hypothesized that the work of adhesion is proportionate to the mechanical strength of an interface [11-13]. However, the calculation processes between the measured contact angles and other interfacial properties are complex, difficult and frequently not well understood.

Rapid, simple and accurate interfacial evaluation methods would be of considerable utility for industrial applications. For this reason, an electrical resistance method, based on Kirchhoff's law, has recently been developed and used for such studies [14]. During mechanical loading the shape of carbon fibers, in a composite, is altered with a concomitant change in electrical resistance. Carbon fibers are used as sensing elements in CFRP due to their electrical conductivity. In some more advanced studies, in CRFP, the carbon fibers were used for both strain sensing and damage sensing. The basic theory, in such studies, was that the movement of carbon fiber could be detected by electrical resistance measurement. During loading, the extent of contact between carbon fibers in a CF tow is altered, and the electrical resistance changes from its initial value [15-17].

In this work, interfacial properties of carbon fiber/polymer composites were evaluated by such electrical resistance measurements. During the wetting process of CF tows by the polymer resins, the change in electrical resistance was recorded and analyzed. The test results for different carbon fibers and polymer resins exhibited different trends. The electrical resistance change was associated with the different wetting conditions, and the interfacial properties were predicted by these electrical resistance measurements. The accuracy of predictions based on the electrical resistance method during polymer resin wetting on CF tow was then assessed by IFSS and ILSS tests.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 MATERIALS and SPECIMENS

In this study two types CF tows, 12 K T700S (Toray Co Ltd., Japan) and 12K T50S-15L (Mitsubishi Co Ltd., Japan), were used as reinforcement materials. Phenolic resol resin (Monsanto Co Ltd., U.S.A.), epoxy resin Bisphenol A type YD-114, YD-128 and bisphenol F type epoxy YDF-175 (Kukdo chemical Co Ltd., Korea) were used as matrix resins. Hardener for the first two epoxy resins was acid anhydride type KBH-1089, and the hardener for YDF-175 was polyamide type G0331.

2.2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

CF tows were wet by two different polymeric resins. Figure 1 shows schematically the wetting process of the tows by the resin. For each specimen, 1g of polymeric resin was dropped on the tow. The resin wetting process was observed by reflecting microscope during a 20 min observation period, and subsequently the different wetting conditions were investigated and compared by contact angle measurements. The length of the CF tows was 5 cm, and the gauge length for electrical resistance measurement [using a 4 wire method (34401A multi-meter, Agilent Tech., U.S.A.)] of the CF tow was 2 cm.

Figure 1: Wetting process of polymer resin on fiber tow.

ILSS evaluation was performed based on ASTM D-2344 [18]. Short beam test specimens were manufactured by hand lay-up with a length of 10 mm, a width of 5mm and a thickness of 2.8 mm. Equation (1) was used to calculate the ILSS:

$$ILSS = \frac{3F}{4bd} \quad (1)$$

where F is the measured maximum load, b is the width, and d is the thickness of the specimen. The IFSS was determined by the microdroplet pull-out test [19]. The embedded length of resin droplet on a single carbon fiber was 150 μm . The IFSS was calculated from the measured pullout force, F , using the following equation:

$$IFSS = \frac{F}{\pi D_f L} \quad (2)$$

where D_f and L are the diameter and the embedded length of the fiber in the matrix. A UTM was used to “pull-out” the resin drop on the carbon fiber at a test speed of 1 mm/min.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Wetting behavior for electric resistance measurement

Figure 2: Contact angle measurement of two polymer resins on CF tow (T700S): phenolic resin (a,b,c,d), Bisphenol F type epoxy (e,f,g,h).

The wetting process of polymer resin on CF tow was investigated by a reflective microscope. Figure 2 shows photographs of wetting angle micro-droplets comparing the of wetting processes for phenolic resin and YDF-175 epoxy resin illustrating the very different wetting patterns exhibited by the two resins. The phenolic resin exhibited much better wettability on the CF tow in that the CF tow was nearly completed wetted by phenolic resin in 1 min. The epoxy YDF-175 exhibited much poorer

wettability of the CF tow, in that the contact angle of the epoxy resin only decreased from 111° to 92° in 1 min. The wettability of different polymer resin was confirmed by contact angle measurements, in that the phenolic resin exhibited significantly better wettability in comparison to the epoxy resins.

Figure 3: Model of test system for electrical resistance measurement.

Figure 3 shows a schematic model that might be used to explain the differences in wetting behavior for the polymer resins on CF tow surfaces. With good wettability the carbon fibers would tend to be better and more separated by the polymer resin. On the other hand, with poor wettability, much less of the CF tow would be wetted and separated by the resin. It is, therefore, anticipated that the interfacial properties between carbon fibers in a tow and a polymeric resin could be evaluated by such wettability measurements at normal pressure and temperature. The electrical resistance of a CF tow would be influenced by the rearrangement of the carbon fibers during the wetting processes. Conversely, it might be anticipated that wettability might be evaluated by the electrical resistance measurement, in that better wettability between CF tow and polymer resin would be associated with larger electrical resistance changes.

Figure 4: Comparison of chemical and morphology of carbon fibers.

Figure 4 shows the surface morphology of carbon fibers and the chemical component by IR test. FT-IR results of two kinds of carbon fibers were nearly same. C-C and C=C peaks proved the hydroxyl groups on fiber surface [20]. The chemical analysis was supposed to confirm the difference of sizing on fiber surface, whereas the chemical component of two carbon fibers was similar. However, the surface morphology of carbon fibers was different. The surface of Toray fibers had clear ridges and striations parallel to the fiber axial direction as a result of the carbon fiber manufacturing process. The Mishubithi fiber only exhibited slight ridges. It was predicted that the smoother surface would provide better wetting effect with resins for Mishubithi fiber.

Figure 5 shows measured electrical resistance change versus time for different polymeric resins on a T700S CF tow. The phenolic resin exhibited largest electrical resistance change during the 20 minutes observation, indicating that the phenolic resin had the best wettability of the CF tow among the four polymer resins. The electrical resistance change of bisphenol A type epoxy resin cured with acid anhydride hardener was larger than that for the bisphenol F type epoxy resin and polyamide type hardener. The epoxy YDF-175 exhibited smallest electrical resistance change, which is attributed to poorer wetting.

Figure 6 shows results similar to those in figure 5 but between T50S-15L CF tow and the polymeric resins. While the electrical resistance results are somewhat similar to those for the T700S CF tow, the electrical resistance changes for some of the resins on the T50S-15L CF tow were higher than on T700S CF tow, which is attributed to the differences in wettability of the carbon fibers by these resins.

Figure 5: Electrical resistance change during wetting process of polymer resin on carbon fiber (T700S).

Figure 6: Electrical resistance change during wetting process of polymer resin on carbon fiber (T50S-15L).

3.2 Mechanical test of interfacial adhesion

Figure 7: IFSS results of different carbon fibers and polymer resins.

Figure 7 shows the IFSS results of carbon fibers for the different polymeric resins. The interfacial properties of the two types of CF tow and polymeric resins were different, and these results exhibited the same basic trends as the electrical resistance measurements. The T50S-15L carbon fiber had better interfacial adhesion than the T700S carbon fiber. These IFSS results of CF tow and polymeric resins were entirely consistent with the wetting test results thereby indicating a proportionate relation between the electrical resistance results and IFSS.

Figure 7: IFSS results of different carbon fibers and polymer resins.

The proportionate relationship between IFSS and electrical resistance change is further supported by the close relationship between the two quantities shown in Figure 8. The relationship between IFSS and electrical resistance change was conjectured for different CF tow and polymer resins, and indeed as shown in Figure 8 both of their trends very closely follow the same quadratic equation line.

Figure 9 shows the ILSS results of CF tow composites with different polymeric resins, and these results very closely duplicate the IFSS results. The relationship and trends between IFSS and the relative changes in resistance shown in Figure 10 further reinforce the conclusion that they are closely related as discussed for figure 8. The rather small differences in the numerical values for ILSS in Figures 9 and 10 and those for IFSS in Figures 7 and 8 are likely due to the specimen types and evaluations, the ASTM D-2344 short beam specimen in the first case and the microdroplet specimen in the second case. In fact, it is stated in the Significance and Use part of ASTM D-2344 that, "In most cases, because of the complexity of internal stresses and the variety of failure modes that can occur in this specimen, it is not generally possible to relate the short-beam strength to any one material property. However, failures are normally dominated by resin and interlaminar properties." Considering this difference the authors find the close agreement between the two test methods very satisfying.

Figure 9: ILSS results of different carbon fibers and polymer resins.

Figure 10: The relationship of ILSS and electric resistance change.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In the research reported here a number studies, all of which were that were thought to be closely related to interfacial properties, were conducted on carbon filled composites with different polymeric matrices. The difference of surface morphology and chemical component of carbon fibers was

investigated by FE-SEM and FT-IR tests. The chemical components of two carbon fibers were similar, whereas Toray fibers had more clear ridges and striations parallel on fiber surface. It was supposed that Mitsubishi fiber had better wettability with resins due to the fewer ridges. These included: electrical resistance changes during resin wetting, static contact angle measurement to determine the wetting of the carbon tow by the resin materials, IFSS measurements by the microdroplet pull-out tests, and IFSS determined by the ASTM D2344 Short Beam Shear Test. It was concluded that these were all interrelated properties all of which are dependent on interfacial phenomena. Improvement in one resulted in improvement of the others. For example, phenolic resin wet the carbon fiber tows better than any of the epoxy resins studied. It also exhibited the largest change in electrical resistance in the 20 minutes wetting test, as well as the largest IFSS and ILSS according to the microdroplet pullout and short beam shear tests. On the other hand, CF tow/epoxy exhibited the poorest carbon tow wettability, the smallest change in resistance and the poorest IFSS and ILSS. For the four systems studied, the relative change in each of these quantities for the materials of a given composite was roughly proportional to the other measured quantities. This may have some very significant practical importance. It may point the way to use quick easy tests to screen and predict other behaviors for composites of different materials and/or processes. Perhaps a simple resistance change test might be used to predict and select good candidate materials, surface processing techniques for high strength composite applications. The proportional relationship between interfacial adhesion and electrical resistance change was obtained by trend fitting line analyses. Ultimately, it was demonstrated that mechanical properties related to interfacial properties might potentially be predicted by electrical resistance measurement and studies of wetting behavior, using empirical formulas and correlations.

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